

The next computing paradigm will emerge from the convergence of computing across the continuum, systems working for both the cyber and physical world, “natural” programming and orchestration, and Everything-as-a-Service. To enable this paradigm, we need high-level programming and reasoning abstractions; mechanisms for discovering properties, services, and devices; and interoperability among them, all united by self-organizing and trustworthy orchestration mechanisms. The European Union and the United States will play important roles in addressing these challenges, and an active research collaboration will boost the effectiveness, and drive the convergence, of solutions.

EU/US White Paper on the Continuum of Computing

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A strategic research collaboration between the EU and the US is starting to enable seamless convergence across the computing continuum, spanning both the physical and cyber worlds. The collaboration represents a new expedition to tame the growing heterogeneity of computing platforms and services across the computing continuum, giving rise to a new computing paradigm.

The web has changed forever the ways in which applications are built and used. Applications are no longer a single piece of executable code deployed on a local computing device. Many modern applications are composed of multiple services published by different providers and executed over highly heterogeneous devices. Machine-to-machine communication appears in a multitude of applications, with execution over vastly different computing platforms (e.g. resource-lean, resource-rich, domain-specific) and networks (e.g. low-bandwidth/high-latency, high-bandwidth/low-latency, wireless, optical). Programming the computing continuum reflects a vision of computing that further decentralizes applications from within large data centres to a paradigm where not only data, but also services migrate dynamically, to be processed where optimal for one or more objectives such as energy, privacy or latency. This will promote enhanced computational capacity at the edge, highly decentralized application designs and privacy-preserving collaborative intelligence.

The ensuing complexity of such systems will require the use of intelligent orchestrators to manage their development, deployment and execution. Trust and protection against malware, together with energy efficiency and sustainability, will become predominant requirements.

This exciting vision of massively distributed cooperative computing across heterogeneous devices and networks is the foremost goal of this emerging collaboration between the EU and the US.

Figure 1: a scene from the HiPEAC Comic Book [1], which evoked the seamlessness of digital technology, discussed in this article

Key insights

- The European Commission and the US National Science Foundation are joining forces to draw upon complementary expertise from the European and American computer and network systems research communities. This aims to catalyse collaborative actions focused on the specification, design and proof-of-concept implementations of robust systems that operate across the computing continuum.
- Computing is increasingly heterogeneous, with individual applications spanning the compute continuum, from resource-constrained processors, memories, and networks to resource-rich edge networks and cloud data centres. There are few unifying abstractions – functional or non-functional – for specifying, implementing, and reasoning about these systems.
- Increased infrastructure utilization – compute, memory, network – yields reductions in energy consumption and operating costs, promoting increasingly service-based implementation work-flows. Everything-as-a-Service (XaaS) across the compute continuum reflects the future of large-scale, next-generation systems.
- Application demands (e.g. latency, budget) and operating context (e.g. resource availability, energy costs, carbon emissions) are often complex and time-varying. Dynamic service provisioning and migration across the compute continuum offers the potential to align application demand with resource availability, limit sensitive data transmission, and minimize energy consumption, carbon emissions and operating costs.
- Optimal operating outcomes depend on multi-objective criteria spanning performance, privacy, security, energy usage, carbon emissions and operating costs – all in the presence of heterogeneous, multi-tenant infrastructure, operating within a dynamic economic and environmental context. The challenge calls for intelligent orchestration tools (e.g. natural configuration interfaces) and services (e.g. learning-based) to assist humans in taming this complexity.

Key recommendations

- Sustain the EU-US joint collaboration in a manner that facilitates research initiatives to address the challenges of robust computing across the continuum.
- Promote the definition and demonstration of unifying specification and programming abstractions for heterogeneous computing across the continuum, capable of addressing functional and non-functional concerns, including performance, privacy, security, energy and emissions.
- Investigate ways to take artificial intelligence (AI) to the edge so that AI engines can assist service provisioning, migration, orchestration and multi-objective optimization of personalized compute services across the continuum.

The web-space extending to IoT devices and the continuum of computing

Massively distributed, cooperative computing across devices and networks will involve applications that are dynamically composed of heterogeneous services, and which evolve constantly, according to environmental changes or other events (internal or external, expected or unexpected). This continuous evolution will be governed by smart orchestrators controlled through specifications provided by human owners via natural interfaces¹. System intelligence, efficiency and safety will be maintained through collective perception, introspection and decision-making, akin to birds flying in swarm formations to meet a shared objective.

One way to conceptualize the envisioned paradigm is to reimagine what the hyperlinks and associated protocols represent in the “traditional” web space in

its first, second and even upcoming third generation. The nodes of this new web-space could expose services or actionable resources, reached via the links and associated protocols, with aggregation defined by the order in which the links are traversed. As with modern web architectures, such orders may be defined statically or arise as a consequence of the link traversal itself.

The computing elements of the envisioned platform are intrinsically heterogeneous and distributed. Approaches such as federation of resources (e.g. compute, storage, sensing, AI acceleration) will be maximally abstracted, hiding all of the technical complexity of their digital nature, and will expose services ready to be orchestrated in the pursuit of specific tasks.

The approach is inherently distributed. Although specific instantiations of the vision can be executed within a centralized data centre (the “cloud approach”),

instances draw maximum value and efficiency when operating in a distributed and heterogeneous computing environment. Decentralized, federated, edge and near-the-user computing offers multiple advantages: it has the potential to (i) reduce an attack surface that spans an ever-increasing deployment of internet-of-things (IoT) sensors and devices, due to local-only communication; (ii) safeguard confidential information by limiting the locality of transfer (e.g. as a gatekeeper for data exchanges); and (iii) be more energy efficient by limiting data exchanges via local processing. It is of paramount importance that cybersecurity considerations remain at the forefront of this design concept, to ensure protection from hackers and other rogue elements.

The legacy of service orientation promotes the consideration of individual resources (e.g. storage, general computing, specialized computing) as individualized

¹ The recourse to natural interfaces is just one possibility in the overall solution space. Abstractions suited for portable and interoperable programming across IoT/edge/cloud platforms also fall within the scope of this action.

services, with the potential for streamlined aggregation through unified protocols and communication infrastructure. Not only does the approach simplify system construction for practitioners, but it opens the door to more collaborative, distributed computing solutions – maximizing resource utilization, reducing energy use and enhancing other “-ilities”.

This new paradigm will herald the advent of composable services associated with document-based contracts that specify functional and non-functional requirements, such as response time and latency, energy requirements and constraints, migration capabilities, cost ceilings, and other elements. Next-generation applications will result from the orchestration of these composable services. To manage the massive complexity of such orchestration, high-level modelling and reasoning abstractions, programming and library abstractions, and operating system services, will all be required, with service aggregation supported through robust “natural” specification and automation mechanisms. Defining fundamental programming, reasoning and execution abstractions that enable operation across the computing continuum lies at the core of this vision.

The complexity of this envisioned orchestration is so significant that humans alone will unlikely be able to tame it: AI support as a first-class concept will be required. In that manner, for example, the smart orchestrators might develop contextual understanding. Intelligent orchestrators might select from a family of implementations (or generate new implementations) to meet non-functional requirements according to user needs and preferences, and will orchestrate their execution accordingly. The orchestrators will also be responsible for in-bound security, verification of trust, and out-bound privacy and confidentiality. These orchestrators will communicate with one another to compose additional, higher-level services, building a sort of “collective intelligence”. They will also ensure the locality of code execution, including their own, **allowing migration of execution**, when opportune, along the continuum.

The ability to discover, compose, and migrate services, and to exchange data across these services requires **high-level abstractions** that can translate into **open protocols** suited for standardization (official or de-facto). To be compatible with existing technologies, these new extensions should operate as **additive enhancements to existing platform solutions**, avoiding the need to start from scratch – for instance, building on existing web-level protocols and interfaces.

Attention to non-functional properties in service interfaces will be important (e.g. latency, localization, environmental footprint, cost), along with methods to expose and compose them. New abstractions or representations will be needed to aid composition and lifecycle management of such service orchestrators and their dependencies, in a manner that hides (but optimally exploits) the intrinsic heterogeneity of end devices.

Complexity, heterogeneity and a lack of interoperability pose significant impediments to the realization of this vision. Defining appropriate abstractions will catalyze interoperability and support human management of the continuum as smart orchestrators emerge. Those abstractions shall provide clear, common representations of functional and non-functional service characteristics, and so they may be assembled in light of those characteristics. Efforts in this direction are already in progress, but a greater **collaborative effort to unify abstractions** is required, from which **tools may be developed** to help build complex, trustworthy systems².

Summary of the challenges

To pursue this vision, the **following challenges must be addressed**:

- Selecting and defining the “right” high-level abstractions to master the complexity of managing a large number of distributed objects, while federating their resources.
- Such abstractions, in all their forms (e.g. programming language abstractions, specification/documentation abstractions, library abstractions, etc.), should

take into account functional and non-functional properties (e.g. time, cost, energy, locality) related to the practical use of services in synergy with the physical world. Due-time, latency and safety-critical guarantees are key to allowing a smooth integration with the physical world, for example controlling industrial processes or automated vehicles, or supporting augmented reality applications.

- A collaborative effort is required to unify those definitions to promote broad interoperability of systems executing on both sides of the Atlantic.
- The ensuing services will require seamless composition, so as to accommodate the heterogeneity of devices, while coping with the dynamics of the environment, in a self-organized and adaptive manner.
- At first, this composition should be simple enough to be carried out easily by humans (with support tools).
- This effort should lead to open protocols that can sustain standardization, whether formal or de-facto.
- There will be a pressing need for tools that leverage these protocols and high-level abstractions to aid the building of complex, trustworthy, service-oriented systems.
- Artificial intelligence provides a natural point of extension upon this foundation, with opportunities for smart orchestrators that enable efficient and adaptive system behaviour, in ways that are fully automated or partially automated with humans-in-the-loop.
- This may include meta-level orchestrating systems to support interoperability and composability – for example, a new generation of operating systems or hypervisors for device orchestration.
- Device discovery and authentication remain challenging tasks in increasingly heterogeneous environments. The emergence of large-scale “deep edge” and near-user computing complicates matters further. There is a need for new search and discovery engines to discover, authenticate and certify the various services.
- Decentralized intelligence will favour self-organizing processes for communication and control, and self-adaptation to

² Various research ambits of software system development will be impacted by this collaboration – programming languages, compilers, runtimes, middleware, etc.

security threats across different applications.

- Local intelligence has the potential to increase trust and trustworthiness, safeguarding privacy and confidentiality through locality constraints (e.g. execution, data sharing). Ensuring protection from hackers or rogue elements is of paramount importance.

Potential avenues of investigation

- Unifying specification and programming language abstractions for heterogeneous systems operating across the computing continuum, including support for both functional and non-functional concerns (e.g. declarative locality constraints).
- Operating system, middleware and runtime services for executing across the computing continuum.
- Compatibility with existing solutions, including communication protocols.
- Resource disaggregation, federation and scheduling across the computing continuum, including compute, memory, network, sensors and actuators.
- Collective perception of aggregate performance, resource utilization and operating environment (e.g. differential energy costs).
- Specification-based, resource-aware service discovery, provisioning, migration and orchestration across the computing continuum.

- AI-assisted service provisioning, migration and orchestration based on multi-objective optimization (e.g. performance, privacy, security, energy, emissions) – i.e. autonomous infrastructure and service management.
- Ensuring trust across the computing continuum, including novel attack models and corresponding security and privacy patterns, in the presence of dynamic provisioning and migration.

References

[1] T. Vardanega et al, “Past, present and future of the Internet and digitally augmented humanity: A HiPEAC Vision,” March 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.hipeac.net/media/public/files/46/7/HiPEAC-2019-Comic-Book.pdf>.

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